

Rewriting Austen: Feminism and the Digital Reimagining of

Pride and Prejudice

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ABSTRACT

The dynamic relationship between literature and social media has evolved into a vibrant space for feminist reinterpretation and cultural critique. Social media platforms are revolutionising the ways in which classical literature is consumed, reimagined and discussed, particularly through a feminist lens. They empower readers and creators to challenge patriarchal narratives embedded in canonical texts by offering alternative interpretations that resonate with contemporary values. The paper explores how digital spaces foster a renewed interest in classical literature, with a desire to uncover and rewrite gendered power structures. Feminist reimagining, which often focus on silenced female characters, abusive dynamics, or the limitations of romantic ideals, circulate widely on social media. Here, they gain cultural traction and provoke viral engagement. These platforms also pave the way for literary discourse by enabling new authors to gain visibility and by encouraging readers to share their personalized, subversive readings. In doing so, they destabilize traditional literary authority and open up transformative feminist dialogues within digital culture.

Keywords: *Feminist Reimagining, Classical Literature, Social Media, Gender, Canon*

In recent decades, feminist scholars and creators have actively engaged in retelling grand narratives, challenging patriarchal ideologies embedded in canonical texts. Works such as Jean Rhys's *Wide Sargasso Sea* (1966), which imagines *Jane Eyre* from Bertha Mason's perspective, and Margaret Atwood's *The Penelopiad* (2005) which reinterprets Homer's

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Odyssey through Penelope's voice, exemplify how feminist retellings foreground marginalized perspectives and interrogate established power structures. The paper seeks to analyse feminist retellings of Jane Austen's narratives, particularly *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*. It tries to explore how contemporary writers reimagine Austen's themes and characters to underscore female agency and give voice to those relegated to the margins of the original narratives.

Jane Austen's works, which are often situated in within the boundaries of Victorian domestic fiction, have long been recognized for their subtle critique of the gender norms and social constraints placed upon women. Her novels focus on the limited economic and social mobility that are available to women. It emphasizes the performative nature of courtship and the nuances of female agency within patriarchal structures. Austen's narratives provide a fertile ground for feminist reinterpretation and expansion. While she wrote with irony and wit to question the world around her, contemporary feminist retellings push these inquiries further by exploring the interiority of sidelined characters. It reimagines plots from alternative viewpoints, and places Austen's concerns in modern or subversive contexts.

Feminist retellings of Austen's novels thereby serve as both a homage as well as an intervention. They preserve the spirit of Austen's social critique while amplifying voices that were previously peripheral, such as those of maids, sisters, rivals and even antagonists. Some examples are Jo Baker's *Longbourn* (2013), which tells *Pride and Prejudice* from the perspective of the Bennet family servants, and *The Other Bennet Sister* (2020) by Janice Hadlow, which focuses on the overlooked Mary Bennet. These exemplify how these reimagined narratives complicate our understanding of Austen's world. Through these reworkings, authors reframe the narratives and reassert the continuing relevance of their themes.

Social media has become a powerful space for feminist storytelling. It offers tools to question and reshape dominant narratives. Unlike traditional literature, which often centers fixed perspectives, digital platforms allow for more fragmented and personal

forms of expression. This shift creates space for women and marginalized voices to speak directly. It challenges stereotypes and revises cultural norms in real time. By blurring the lines between public and private, performance and authenticity, social media also invites audiences to engage more intimately with questions of gender, identity and power. This makes it an ideal platform for feminist reimagining of familiar stories.

A notable example of feminist literature wielding social media as a powerful tool is *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, a modern adaptation of *Pride and Prejudice*. It uses elements from social media in order to engage their audience and reimagine the classic novel. The work is an apt fit for the case study as it takes on the form of a vlog- a popular use of people to document their lives in the 21st century and one that they may relate to.

Introduction to the Series

The Lizzie Bennet Diaries is the traditional story of *Pride and Prejudice* set in the modern day. Told in the vlog-style by the eponymous Elizabeth “Lizzie” Bennet, each episode is encapsulated within two to eight minutes. The common setting of the show is within Lizzie’s bedroom, making Lizzie the narrator to the major events that happen offscreen. She is often accompanied by her sisters Lydia and Jane and best friend Charlotte, who offer their perspectives on the events.

However, the canonical narrative undergoes a significant transformation in this series through the integration of digital culture and online interaction. In doing so, the adaptation reimagines key characters. It presents them in ways that often challenge or subvert the dominant interpretations found in the original novel. This reconfiguration of character not only shifts audience perception but also alters the trajectory of the plot itself. It offers new meanings and interpretations that depart markedly from the literary canon.

Mrs Bennet as a Product of Patriarchal Pressure

The series metamorphoses etiquettes of Austen's day to the modern times. Dowries take form of student-loan debt, weddings take the place of fancy balls, and gossip is meted out via text and Facebook.

“It is a truth universally acknowledged that a single man in possession of a good fortune must be in want of a wife.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 0:00-0:09)

This popular quote from the novel is cleverly adapted into the very first episode of the series, where Lizzie shows it embroidered on a shirt. Semantically, the implications of the usage of the quotes in the show and book remain the same. However, the series attempts to make a more whimsical spectacle out of it by highlighting the hysterical and nonsensical nature of Mrs. Bennet.

“So my mom belongs to a class of parents I like to call the 2.5 WPF Club. What's the 2.5 WPF Club? It stands for a home with 2.5 kids and a white picket fence.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 0:31- 0:40)

The statement is made in order to highlight the ludicrousness of Mrs. Bennet's character. While the sentiment may have held true to Austen's period, the elements of the dialogues and the use of the traditional quote is employed to serve a comical purpose in the show. It adapts the plot to the 21st century in order to underscore the shift in the states of the mindsets of both generations.

“It's not like we're all going to put our lives on hold because some rich single guy dropped from the sky.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 2:30-2:37)

The statement sounds quite paradoxical as the creator tries to show the lack of change of intentions within both works.

“Yes, my mother is obsessed with marrying off her daughters but, uh, anyone who watches the videos can see that she cares about us and in her own way wants what's best.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 3:50-4:05)

This instance supports the argument that Lizzie's references to Mrs. Bennet are deliberately framed in a comical light. She uses humour as a means to critique traditional expectations. At the same time, these portrayals chart Lizzie's character development from someone prone to prejudice and quick judgements to a more empathetic and self-aware individual.

Negotiating Authority in Victorian and Modern Patriarchy

Another notable example is the adaptation of the scene in which Mr. Bennet is urged to meet Bing Lee. In Austen's original, Mrs. Bennet's insistence aligns with Victorian norms of social propriety and marital strategy. However, in *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, this moment is reinterpreted through a comedic lens, portraying Mrs. Bennet as overly dramatic and intrusive. By doing so, the adaptation transforms the theme of social propriety into a critique of outdated conventions. She attempts to use humour to question their relevance in a modern context.

“What's keeping Mom “happy” at the moment is that she's decided we can't go over to meet Bing Lee like normal people. For some reason, Dad has to go over and introduce the rest of us.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 0:25-0:30)

Victorian traditions dictated that the male head of the household held authority over matters concerning his daughters, including courtship. A suitor was expected to seek the father's permission before pursuing a relationship. It reinforced the patriarchal view of women as dependents or property within the domestic sphere. However, in a 21st century context, such conventions are largely viewed as outdated and even absurd. The feminist movement and contemporary discourse on gender equality challenge these norms, framing them as relics of a bygone era. Subsequently, modern adaptations often use these traditions as a vehicle for satire or critique. It exposes the inherent objectification of women in historical customs and reframes them through a critical, often humorous, lens.

The Empowered Arc of Lydia Bennet as a Survivor

The series also navigates the feminist transformation in one of its main characters and plot, particularly the scandal involving Lydia Bennet and George Wickham. In Austen's original, Lydia's elopement and subsequent forced marriage to Wickham were portrayed as the best possible solution, given the Victorian standards of propriety. However, in modern feminist discourse, such a resolution is highly problematic.

In the series, Lydia is portrayed as a college student who describes herself as feisty, energetic and unapologetic. It is a characterization that emphasizes her autonomy along with her vulnerability. The series reframes her entanglement with Wickham as an emotionally manipulative and predatory relationship. It aligns more closely with contemporary understandings of grooming and consent. Rather than resolving Lydia's arc with marriage, it chooses to critique the original's compromise and gives her a path of healing and self-empowerment. In doing so, Lydia's narrative is reclaimed and it challenges the patriarchal structures that once demanded silence, shame or sacrifice from women in her position.

“Lydia. We are all very proud that she's now officially too old to be in any television reality show about being pregnant in high school. Seriously, she's like a puppy. A cute, never-know-where-she-sleeps, puppy.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 1:03-1:08)

The web series offers a more critically satisfying and also ethically aware resolution the relationship between Wickham and Lydia. Rather than romanticizing or downplaying the scandal as the original novel does, the series presents Wickham's actions as a calculated and predatory attempt at revenge against Lizzie and Darcy. He does so by manipulating Lydia into a non-consensual and emotionally exploitative sexual relationship, and even going so far as to record it without her informed consent. This reframing not only modernizes the narrative but also aligns it with conversations about digital consent, emotional abuse and victim-blaming.

“He said that I didn’t love him as much as he loved me, and I needed to prove it. So I said okay. So that he wouldn’t leave.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 5:11-5:28)

In modern terms, Wickham would most accurately be described as a red flag, i.e. a manipulative individual skilled in gaslighting and emotional exploitation. His relationship with Lydia exemplifies what would now be widely recognized as toxic, marked by manipulation, imbalance of power, and psychological harm. While such relationships are regrettably common in the present day, the series refuses to normalize or romanticize this dynamic. Instead, it offers a nuanced and empathetic portrayal of Lydia as a survivor rather than a cautionary tale.

The adaptation takes significant strides in portraying the psychological trauma experienced by victims of predatory relationships. Lydia’s character is given emotional depth and narrative space to articulate her confusion, hurt and eventual journey towards healing. This is something Austen’s original narrative denies. In contrast to the novel’s portrayal, where Lydia remains flippant and seemingly unaware of the consequences of her actions, the series emphasizes the emotional damage of Wickham’s betrayal. The sex tape scandal functions as a powerful metaphor for digital violations of privacy and consent. The threat of such a video going public foreshadow the irreversible harm it could cause, especially in a world where anything on the internet lasts forever. Lizzie’s recognition of the danger shows a modern and compassionate awareness of how such an event could derail Lydia’s future, socially, emotionally and professionally. This modernized narrative not only foregrounds Lydia’s victimhood but also her resilience. It offers a redemptive arc grounded in personal growth and sisterly support.

“Everyone who watches these knows how I felt. That he never made me do anything, so just tell me that I didn’t get what I had coming, Lizzie” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 5:51-6:04).

In Austen’s work, Wickham ultimately escapes serious consequences for his actions by marrying Lydia. This outcome, while resolving the immediate social crisis, was met with

considerable disapproval by readers. They viewed the marriage as a deeply troubling union. Wickham's manipulative behaviour and Lydia's naiveness created a dynamic in which she was clearly exploited, while the Bennet's family reputation teetered on the brink of ruin due to the scandal of elopement. Although the marriage supposedly restores the social order, it is widely interpreted as a grim resolution. It also predicted long-term unhappiness for Lydia. Her inability- or refusal- to recognize Wickham's true nature has been criticized by readers, further contributing to her portrayal as immature, impulsive and foolish.

From Compliance to Agency: The Journey of Jane Bennet

Jane Bennet is an up-and-coming fashion designer, who dreams to be independent and free. Much like the traditional version of Jane, however, she too is softspoken and shy. She chooses to maintain a neutral admiration to the world around her.

“And then there's the eldest Bennet sister, Jane. Practically perfect in every way.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 1:18-1:21)

Jane is portrayed as a much gentler being than her counterpart in the original. Marriage being at the back of her mind, this character tends to take on the role of a caretaker, not only for her sisters, but also her work, friends, and the infamous Bing Lee.

“She's doing so much more with her life than prancing around as some trophy wife.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 2:15-2:19)

While the series retains the central plot of a romantic relationship between Jane and Bing Lee, it adapts the storyline with modern sensibilities and character agencies. In the original, Jane's extended stay at Netherfield is prompted by her sudden illness. In reality, it is an event orchestrated by Mrs. Bennet as part of her strategic attempt to secure a marriage between her eldest daughter and Mr. Bingley. In the series, this scenario is updated into the remodelling of the Bennet household, serving as a convenient pretext for Jane and Lizzie to temporarily move in with the Lee family. It is a plan similarly encouraged by the scheming Mrs. Bennet in the hope of advancing Jane's romantic

prospects. As in Austen's text, the couple fall in love and appear to be a compatible and affectionate couple.

However, the series deviates meaningfully from the canon events during their eventual reunion. In Austen's novel, Jane readily accepts Bingley back with joy and little hesitation. This emphasizes her forgiving and gentle nature. In contrast, the Jane of the series expresses clear frustration and emotional conflict upon Bing Lee's return. Her response is not one of immediate fixing, but of thoughtful resistance. It portrays a reflection of her growth and the assertion of her personal boundaries.

After the scandal of Lydia and Wickham, Jane loses her job, but also manages to secure a more promising opportunity in New York. This new chapter in her life coincides with Bing Lee's return. Jane chooses to pursue her career aspirations rather than risk sacrificing them for the sake of rekindling the relationship. She even avoids telling Bing of her departure, fearing that he might attempt to convince her to stay. When he eventually confronts her at the Bennet household, Jane firmly refuses to remain behind. She chooses her independence over romantic reconciliations.

This highlights Jane's evolution from a passive figure of romantic idealism into a self-assured, career-driven woman. It illustrates how the series reimagines Austen's characters reflecting modern values of autonomy and self-realization.

“This is a really incredible opportunity, and there's no way I'm gonna miss it. How unfair would it be for you to ask that of me? And this fresh start, it's not enough for me to just up my career.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 1:36- 1:48)

Jane's words serve a number of purposes here. A deeper analysis of it reveals three motives in particular- the retelling, a feminist outlook and a practical decision.

“On opening the door, she perceived her sister and Bingley standing together over the hearth, as if engaged in earnest conversation; and had this led to no suspicion, the faces of both, as they hastily turned round and moved away from each other, would have told it all.” (Austen 402)

The reinterpretation of Jane and Bingley's relationship in the series offers a critique of the submissiveness often attributed to Victorian women. In Austen's work, the separation between Jane and Bingley is instigated by Bingley himself. He is influenced by both Mr. Darcy and his sister Caroline. Despite this, he faces little to no consequence for his decision to abandon the relationship. However, Jane is passively presented as waiting to be reclaimed, served on a silver platter. This dynamic reflects the era's social norms, where women were expected to forgive, forget and remain emotionally available for the men who once dismissed them.

In contrast, the Jane of the series emerges as a feminist figure. She is strong, principled and self-possessed. She prioritizes the emotional well-being of her family and the security of her career, refusing to compromise her personal goals for the sake of romantic reconciliation. Although she remains courteous and kind, she proves capable of asserting boundaries when necessary. Even Lizzie, who had previously criticized Jane for her excessive graciousness and optimism, comes to respect her sister's assertiveness and supports her decision to stand firm.

The series' emphasis on practicality over romantic idealism is fascinating to note. Modern literature and popular media romanticize the trope of protagonists abandoning everything- careers, homes, even countries- in pursuit of love. Examples include *Brooklyn*, where Eilis ultimately chooses love over her past life in Ireland, and *The Hundred-Foot Journey*, where a chef sacrifices a prestigious career in Paris to reunite with a love interest. In contrast, Jane's decision not to stay for Bing Lee disrupts this familiar narrative arc. It reflects a grounded, rational perspective that puts long-term fulfilment and self-respect over impulsive emotional decisions.

Rather than immediately reuniting, Jane and Bing choose to rebuild their connection gradually. They stress on the need for trust and mutual respect. Jane rightly says that a tentative reconciliation is not a sufficient reason to pass up an exceptional professional opportunity in New York. This choice would have been unthinkable in the Victorian age, especially for women. Yet in the 21st century, it reflects the lived experiences of many

modern women who have been empowered by feminist movements and inspired by social media narratives that celebrate autonomy and ambition.

An admirable aspect of this modern retelling is Bing Lee's reaction to Jane's decision. In an age where media frequently portrays men as reacting with hostility, entitlement or manipulation when rejected with traits labelled as red flag behaviour, Bing Lee defies this expectation. He does not pressure Jane, attempt to guilt her into staying, or assert control over her choices. Instead, he accepts her decision with maturity, recognizing the importance of her personal and professional growth. This deviation from toxic masculinity offers a welcome counter-narrative and contributes to the broader aspect of the series in the quest of independence of women.

“Jane, I’m not asking you to stay. I’m asking if I can go with you.” (The Lizzie Bennet Diaries 1:50-1:55)

Bing Lee's character arc in the series undergoes significant development, and transforms him from a somewhat passive and socially-influenced figure into a more self-aware and autonomous individual. Early in the series, Bing is portrayed as someone who, much like his original counterpart, may have expected Jane to compromise her aspirations for the sake of their relationship. He may have even contemplated leaving if she did not conform to those expectations. However, this new version of Bing shows his emotional maturity. Rather than reacting with offense or detachment to Jane's decision to prioritize her career, Bing chooses to support her. He expresses a willingness to relocate with her to New York. Unlike the original Mr. Bingley who might have considered such a rejection as a slight to his honour, Bing responds with understanding and introspection.

A major aspect of his growth lies in his professional trajectory. Initially a medical student, Bing ultimately opts to leave the field as he realizes that it fails to bring him personal fulfilment. Instead, he chooses a career in social work, showing a deliberate move away from the societal expectations of prestige and wealth and towards a more meaningful and value-driven life. The series draws attention to his reflection journey. It allows him to make independent choices free from the influence of his family or friends. When Jane

learns of his decision, including his renewed purpose and willingness to act according to his own values, she reconsiders her stance and is open to a renewed partnership on equal footing.

Conclusion

While the series presents itself as a progressive adaptation of a literary classic, its engagement with feminist discourse is tentative. By reimagining characters and embracing the aesthetics of digital culture, the events offers a fresh take on the original narrative.

However, it also operates within established social and narrative frameworks. It also avoids any substantial challenge to the dominant ideological structures that it inherits. As such, the adaptation avoids disrupting the deeper framework of gender and romance that shaped the original text. The characters may be more self-aware and the storytelling more interactive, but the underlying message remains largely unchanged.

Rather than presenting a bold reimagining, the series offers a softened, more palatable version of the feminist critique. It is thoughtful but not so radical, reflective but not transformative. In this way, the series mirrors many contemporary adaptations that seek progress without confrontation, leaving the audience with a version of feminism that is engaging but ultimately limited in its reach.

References

“Episode 1: My Name is Lizzie Bennet.” *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, created by Bernie Su and Hank Green, performance by Ashley Clements, YouTube, uploaded by Pemberley Digital, 9 Apr. 2012, www.youtube.com/watch?v=KisuGP2lcPs.

“Episode 2: My Sisters – Problematic to Practically Perfect.” *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, created by Bernie Su and Hank Green, performance by Ashley Clements,

YouTube, uploaded by Pemberley Digital, 12 Apr. 2012,
www.youtube.com/watch?v=Krh1koDUhVg.

“Episode 3: Career Defining.” *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, created by Bernie Su and Hank Green, performance by Ashley Clements, YouTube, uploaded by Pemberley Digital, 16 Apr. 2012,
www.youtube.com/watch?v=zKblfElogzE.

“Episode 6: Snobby Mr. Darcy.” *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, created by Bernie Su and Hank Green, performance by Ashley Clements, YouTube, uploaded by Pemberley Digital, 23 Apr. 2012,
www.youtube.com/watch?v=KY1fVnmbeIE.

“Episode 83: Questions and Answers.” *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, created by Bernie Su and Hank Green, performance by Ashley Clements and Laura Spencer, YouTube, uploaded by Pemberley Digital, 7 Mar. 2013,
www.youtube.com/watch?v=Uq3RIE3wJ7A.

“Episode 86: I Like Being Weird.” *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, created by Bernie Su and Hank Green, performance by Mary Kate Wiles, YouTube, uploaded by Pemberley Digital, 14 Mar. 2013,
www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZtyZL3iMKCK.

“Episode 87: Adorbs.” *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, created by Bernie Su and Hank Green, performance by Mary Kate Wiles, YouTube, uploaded by Pemberley Digital, 18 Mar. 2013, www.youtube.com/watch?v=WaXvbLxa3jE.

“Episode 92: Grief Without Pity.” *The Lizzie Bennet Diaries*, created by Bernie Su and Hank Green, performance by Mary Kate Wiles, YouTube, uploaded by Pemberley Digital, 25 Mar. 2013,
www.youtube.com/watch?v=0Kx9FHqMUbE.

“The Lizzi Bennet Diaries Wiki.” Fandom, thelizziebennetdiaries.fandom.com/. Accessed 28 May 2025.

Jenkins, Henry. *Textual Poachers: Television Fans and Participatory Culture*. Routledge, 1992.

The Lizzie Bennet Diaries. YouTube, channel created by Pemberley Digital, www.youtube.com/@LizzieBennet. Accessed 28 May 2025.

Wilkinson, Amy. “Remember Pride and Prejudice? It’s Back- in Vlog Form!” The A.V. Club, 11 Sept. 2012, www.avclub.com/remember-pride-and-prejudice-it-s-back-in-vlog-form-1798231147.